

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B096
Date: 19 May 2005
Take Off 09:52:58
Landing: 14:31:04
Flight Time 4h38m06

Campaign: CWVC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Chilbolton Radar

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Charlie Whittaker	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Flight Manager Training	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	CCN /CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	SID2 Diagnostics 1	Edwin Hirst	University of Hertfordshire
9	SID2 Diagnostics 2	Richard Greenaway	University of Hertfordshire
10	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
11	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
12	CPI	Paul Connolly	University of Manchester
13			
14			
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19			
20			

Flight Track:

B096 Track 19-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b096
 Date: 19 May 2005
 Project: CWVC
 Location: Chilboten

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093406		INU to nav	0.33 kft	115	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093806		taxy start	0.32 kft	115	
093819		taxy start	0.32 kft	117	
095258		T/O	0.31 kft	211	from cranfield
100223		asp open	6.0 kft	218	
100636		jw zero	6.0 kft	184	
102056	105933	Profile 1	3.7 - 30.0 kft	251	
103442		Profile 1	17.0 kft	252	interrupt
103833		Profile 1	17.0 kft	082	resume
104911		Profile 1	27.0 kft	077	interrupt
105515		Profile 1	27.2 kft	259	resume
111048	111447	Run 1	23.0 kft	075	
112245	112902	Run 2	20.0 kft	253	
113725	114256	Run 3	10.5 kft	076	
114737	120012	Run 4	10.0 kft	235	
120515	121156	Run 5	9.0 kft	076	
121513	121617	Profile 2.1	9.0 - 10.0 kft	261	
121618	121724	Profile 2.2	10.0 - 9.1 kft	243	
121725	121926	Run 6	9.1 - 9.0 kft	252	
121926	122023	Profile 3.1	9.0 - 8.0 kft	251	
122023	122129	Profile 3.2	8.0 - 9.0 kft	253	
122129	122332	Run 7	9.0 kft	252	
122332	122432	Profile 4.1	9.0 - 9.9 kft	251	
122432	122543	Profile 4.2	9.9 - 9.1 kft	249	
122543	122749	Run 8	9.1 - 9.0 kft	250	
123326	123634	Profile 5.1	9.0 - 12.0 kft	078	
123634	123745	Profile 5.2	12.0 - 11.0 kft	077	
123745	123949	Run 9	11.0 kft	081	
124311	124422	Profile 6.1	11.0 - 10.1 kft	254	
124422	124830	Profile 6.2	10.1 - 14.0 kft	248	
124830	125055	Run 10	14.0 kft	252	
125135	125547	Profile 7	14.0 - 10.1 kft	251	
130007	130516	Profile 7.2	10.0 - 5.0 kft	087	
130616	130833	Run 11	5.0 kft	077	
131154	131451	Profile 8	5.0 - 8.0 kft	266	
131451	132458	Run 12	8.0 kft	250	
132846	133104	Profile 9	8.0 - 10.0 kft	084	
133105	133656	Run 13	10.0 kft	078	
134027	134659	Profile 10	10.0 - 15.9 kft	252	
135045	135500	Run 14	16.0 kft	090	
140835		asp closed	5.0 kft	351	
143104		Land	0.35 kft	308	Cranfield
		Apron 2			52 04.36N 000 35.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B096 Track 19-MAY-05

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci K.N. BOWER

CWVC

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date **19/05/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:03:04	T	6000'	196	51.9N/1.4W	Clear Air CCN sample taken - approx 15 mins at 6000'
10:07:50	T				descending to 5000' ATC
10:09:26	T	5000	183	51.6/1.4W	New level reached
10:14:50	T	5000	182	51.3/1.4	Drizzle getting big 800-1000m CPT
10:17:14		5000			Descending to 3500' for start P1
					(Remaining along 1 st Radial - will start P1 at 3500')
10:20:56	P1 start	3500'			P1 (to 240'00) on E-W leg
10:24:12	P1	7100'	250		1.67°C / -11.03°C 12m/s/221 deg 766mb
		8700'			Radar ⇒ turbo at 2.5km 8200' - windshear?
		9400'			a little turbulence -
10:29		11,500'			Photo Front Right
					(M.Sci / Flight Sci - B&B)
10:29:50		13420			Photo ahead - Ci above.
10:33:20		15500	252		-14.86 -21.61
10:34:10					Ice ahead, low N, CPT, 2D contain this
10:34:22	P1 int	17000			(MODIS O/P - Ci are around + S. - ppt around is quite small -
10:36:56	P1 int	17000	turn continues		to turn onto a W-E P1 leg. -16.71/-17.97°C
					14m/s/248° 526 mb.
10:38:33	P1 retransmitting	FL170			clear air W-E leg.
					azimuth 253° True.
		25000			35.
					worked on radar 5km alt
10:41:11	P1 int	27000'			Intermittent - left them back on E-W leg.

7000 221°
17000 244°

Ci ice ahead - rather than where we are - difficult to pick up

Mission Scientist's Log

Misc K.N. BOWER CWVC

Flight No **B.096**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					shut runs 40km from Chilbolton
					FL 230 in Cirrus
10:55:15	P1	FL 270			Profile P1 resumed
10:59:33	P1 end	F300	257		35m/s / 264° -47.53 / -48.88°C 302mb
11:00:40			256	51.04/2.1W	photo in descent - alt to right
	R1 start	23000		51.0 / 2.4W	Inbound to Chilbolton - looking for Ci
					(2DC few particles - CPI - seeing particles)
					(Q-Radar - Plume over Chilbolton)
					Cloud - gradually lowering 4½ km - 7½ km
					14000 - 24000 - shut runs desc to
					Chilbolton - 5-6 km 19-20,000'
					length of legs - shorter the better 20-25k
					12½ miles from Chilbolton
					20 mile legs
11:10:48	R1 start	FL 230			
11:14:47	R1 end	FL 230			CPI - 2D seeing particles
11:17:50					last 1 minute seeing Ci partial (2D/CPI)
					Ci - above us now
11:22:45	R2	FL 200			- No cloud here -
					(10-14000 ish - good belt - says run 13000)
					(Captain
					Cloud - 5-7km breaking up
					Subsaturated H ₂ O - 12,500 -
11:29:02	R2 end	FL 200			Capt - abandons run - heading E-W - descend
					to 13000, to do W-E run SLE to Chil.

shut runs

50

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: K.N. BOWER CWVC

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:35:08					No cloud at 13000' → 11000'
	R	FL110			Inbound - still no cloud (-5.24/-18.9°C 20/228')
11:37:25	R3 ↓	FL105			10500' 60km out
11:40:46	R3	FL105	80°	SI.0/1.9W	Seeing small drops -4.0/-8.5° 21/234 20sec out -
11:42:40	R				
11:42:56	R3 end	FL105			(P. Down actv) - terminate run
11:47:57	R4 st	FL100	240	SI.1/1.5W	West away from Chil -3.03/-2.93°C 19m/s/21
11:49:09	R4	FL100		SI.1/1.6W	CP7 water small particles + water ← 2D
11:50:45	R4		251	SI.0/1.8W	bumps -3.28/-3.23 18m/s/221° 696mb only seen LW - no ice CP7 solar thin run
11:52:15	R4				2D - only Water.
11:54:13			250	SI.9/2.2W	Aircraft - seen on radar - v clear -
12:00:12	R4 end				and descends
12:09:15	R5	FL090			(20041s) True MS 234, Indicated 200
12:08:17	R5	FL090	77	SI.0/2.1	723mb: -2.17/-1.14 18m/s/228
12:11:56	R5 end				only LWC
					see echos 3h - 60-70-8h -
					closed 10 mls - 60 mls
12:15:	P2.1				descent 1000' in scrubth - to FL100
12:16:17	P2.2				descent 1000' to FL90
12:17:24	R6	FL090			
12:19:36	P3.1				end R6, stop - (at base T _v 0°/-10°C)
	P3.2				45km Outbound
12:21:29	R7	FL090			-1.77/-0.65

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci K.N. BOWER

CWVC

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:23:32	P4.1				climb 1000' to 10000
12:24:32	P4.2				descent 1000' to 9000'
12:25:43	R8 st	FL90			
					very extensive cloud over 80km layer
					10000 - 12000' where thick layer
12:27:49	R8 end				cloud SIC water unheated from rad ⁿ part of view
					Broadband radiometer level flight above
12:33:26	PS start	FL90 ↑	78	50.9/2.4	9000 ↑ -2.87 -3.98°C, 19 m/s/226, 675.1
12:36:34	end PS/P5.2		76	51.0/2.0	FL120 ↓ -6.16, -37.81 17/233
	P5.2	11200'			661
12:37:45	P5.2 end/R9	FL110	80	51.0/1.9W	Bumpy
12:39:49	R9 end/turn	FL110	140	51.0/1.7	22/224° -5.03 9.06 669.25
					Radar - current SIC layer - peaking out at 70km range - Pilot ✓
12:43:	P6.1	FL110 → 100	242	51.1/1.6W	Proble descent to FL100 681mb -4.0/5.6
12:44:22	P6.2	FL100-110	248	51.0/1.7W	680mb -4.69/4.97 17m/s/220
					CPI - all LW all saw - 2D too
12:47:09	P6.2		251	51.0/2.0W	-7.12 / -36.19 16/227 680mb
12:48:30	R10	14000'			end P6.2
12:50:55	R10 end	FL140			descent to ~ 6-7000'
12:51:35	P7 start				
12:53:06	P7	descent	251	50.9/2.4	-8.32 / -27.25 17/240' 672mb
					-seeing thick cloud above

descent ↑ 14000

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci - K.N. BOWEN CNVC

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Date **19/03/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:55:42	P7 int	FL100			intermittent - beam
13:00:07	P7 recon	FL100 ↓	85	50.9/26	recommencing P7 down to FL50
13:00:55	P7	~9200			-1.15°C / -20.26 18 m/s / 237° 716 mb
13:03:55	P7	6800	76	50.9/23	Cloud tops.
13:05:16	P7 end	FL5000			
13:06:16	R11st				Large droplets - 2D - CP1 was seeing large droplets
13:08	R11 end				beam - profile clouds to FL80
13:10:12					SD in range - 1 km high - Radar sees in.
13:11:00					Arriving CB - broad section - large / small droplets
					2D same (just prior to this)
13:11:54	P8 st	FL50 ↑	264	51.0/17W	+4.2/2.1°C 12 m/s / 232° 816 mb.
13:14:51	P8 end / P12 start	FL60	250	51.0/19W	-0.05/0.08 18 m/s / 220° 752
					Cloud gap -
					Radar → after this run below cloud - middle layer @ 10000' - to check cloud is same
13:19:27	R12	FL80	250	50.9/2.3W	Photo of cloud gap
13:21:00	R12				In cloud again - tops of lower level.
13:24:58	R12 end	@FL80			terminating to do profile ascent
					intermittent interpen on frequency
	P9 start				
	P9	7	72°		
13:31:05	end P9				-1.89/19.01
13:34:16					seen few - 10s with ice crystals
13:36:56	end P10	FL100			we were not on cloud so attempting to do Ci above - then
13:40:27	start P10				profile to 16000

35

E-W

N-E

E-W

extension - best high echo Ci - 60-70 km 5 km 16000' range end 80 km
 radar - inbound 16000 - 8 km range height - 5 km 16-18000

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	500 psi	130	130
POST FLIGHT	400 psi	130	130

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.35	0.4	1.108	0.068	0.479
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
OK	34.10	1.07	7.15	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1	-2	-1	-3	-2	-1	
NO (ppbV)	0.07	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.09	
NO₂ (ppbV)	1.44	1.47	1.51	1.56	1.59	1.61	
NO_x (ppbV)	1.66	1.61	1.55	1.50	1.51	1.7	
SO₂ (ppbV)	-2.91	-1.91	-2.36	-2.61	-1.91	-2.36	

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS
CO took a long time to warm up – not warmed up by security check

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)							
		19/5/05 HANGAR		82.95		87.11		7226.01							
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		89.89		83.04		7464.61		45.49		7.15					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample			
10:17:23		5000ft		34		0.7		0.8		0.068		1.204		0.431	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		86.74		81.90		7103.34		48.08		7.15					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample			
10:37:46:		170		34.01		0.7		0.8		1.042		0.064		ALARM	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		84.24		82.48		6948.29		49.64		7.14					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample			
10:51:54		270		33.91		0.7		0.75		0.971		0.067		ALARM	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		82.77		82.85		6857.57		50.0		7.13					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample			
11:07:39		230		33.96		0.7		0.75		0.998		0.066		ALARM	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		82.13		83.04		6820.33		50		7.14					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample			
11:25:40		200		33.95		0.7		0.75		1.032		0.064		ALARM	

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

Time	Flight Level	CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
11:38:38	110	81.98	84.41	6919.93	50	7.12		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.93	0.7	0.75	OK	OK	ALARM	
12:07:56		CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		81.85	84.08	6882.20	50	7.14		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
13:11:54		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.88	0.7	0.75	OK	OK	OK	
		13:34:12	100	CO				
				Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
81.04	84.21			6824.30	50	7.14		
Flows (LPM unless stated)								
13:50:19	160	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.91	0.6	0.8	OK	OK	OK	
		13:50:19	160	CO				
				Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
81.18	83.01			6738.28	50	7.14		
Flows (LPM unless stated)								
13:50:19	160	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.96	0.7	0.75	OK	OK	ALARM	

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B096

Date: 19/05/05

Operator: PAPJ

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
111048	10		612								RUN@230
1112	10		612								
111447											
112245	15		614								END OF RUN START RUN 2 @200
1124	15		614								
1126	30		614								
1128	15		614								
112902	50		614		40	200	8				END RUN 2 START RUN 3 @105
113725	30		614								
1139	10		614								
1141	14		616								
1142	30		618		400	75	11				END RUN 3 START RUN 4 @ 100
114256											
114741	20		642		400	75	11				
1150	160		648		200	100	11				
1152	6		652								
1154	6		665								
1156	18		666								
120012	35		670								END OF RUN 4 START RUN 5 @ 090
120515	40		680		400	150	12				
1207	100		703		200	100	12				
1209	50		728		200	200	12				
1211	5		739		200	100	12				
121186											END OF RUN 5 START P2.1
121513	10		805		100	100	12				END P2.2 START RUN 6 AND END 2.2
121617	5		811								
121724	6		812								
1219	20		814		100	150	12				
121926	40		819		100	400	1				END 6 AND START 3.1
12											
1221	30		828		500	300	1				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B096

Date: 19/5/05

Operator: PAPJ

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
1223	30	0.5	835		200	200	1				
122332											END OF 7 START P4.1
1224	12	0.5	845		600	200	12				
122432											END 4.1 START 4.2
1225	40	0.4	852		70	200	12				
122543											END 4.2 START 8
1226	40	0.6	860								
122749											END 8
123326	11	0.1	862								START 5.1 @ 090
1235	100	0.3	867		500	300	12				
1236	20	0.09	869								
123634	25	0.1	869								END 5.1 START 5.2
123949											END 5.2 START 9
124311											START 6.1
1244											RUN 10 @140
1250	30	0.09	877								
125055											END 10
125135											START
1252	30	0.09	877								
1253	30	0.09	877								
1255	30	0.09	877								
1301	60	0.09	877								
130616											START 11 @050
1307	100	0.1	953		16	600	1				
											END 11
131154											START 8 @050
131250	50	0.09	955		30	300	1				060
131350	200	0.5	961		200	400	1				070
131451											080 END 8

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B096**

Date: 19/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	Y
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS		N
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B096

Date: 19/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. SID fault-finding during flight.